

TITLE

SPECIFICATIONS

Size	1.25 Inch ID
SKU	C303202
Input Pressure	0.41 MPa
Radial Load Max	289 N
Thrust Load Max	645 N
Axial Stiffness	87 N/ μ m
Radial Stiffness	34 N/ μ m
Flowrate on Shaft	6.13 - 9.91 NLPM
Air Gap at maximum recommended load	150 micro-inches
Thrust Bushing Inside Diameter (ID)	1.2508 in +.0002/- .0000
Bushing Outside Diameter (OD)	50mm
Thrust Face Outside Diameter (OD)	76.2mm
Thrust Bushing Length	66.675mm
Thrust Bushing Weight	238 grams
Housing Material/Finish	Aluminum/Anodized
Porous Media Material	Carbon
Recommended Shaft Outside Diameter (OD)	1.250 in +.0000 / -.0003
Recommended Mounting Bore	1.990 in +/- .002
Maximum Allowable Pressure Supply	0.689 MPa
Resolution	Infinite
Maximum Speed	50 m/sec
Common Shaft Materials	Anodized aluminum, stainless steel, nickel plated steel, ceramics, glass
For Specifications contact New Way Technical Support at:	610-364-3465